

TEACHING GRAMMATICAL STRUCTURES IN SECONDARY CLASSROOM ATMOSPHERE

Khakimova Dilshoda Oybek qizi

Faculty of English philology and teaching, Uzbekistan State World Languages University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
dilshodaa.khakimova@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

This article aims to give data about importance of grammar and methods, techniques of teaching grammatical rules and structures in secondary school. In the article, there are advised methods to teach grammar with concise rules, and examples are also provided.

Key words: grammar, language structure, advantage, techniques, methods, approach, teachers, language, deductive method, inductive method, inductive-deductive method, incidental method.

ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИХ СТРУКТУР В АТМОСФЕРЕ СРЕДНЕГО КЛАССА

Хакимова Дилшоода Ойбек кизи

Факультет английской филологии и преподавания, Узбекский государственный университет мировых языков, Ташкент, Узбекистан
dilshodaa.khakimova@mail.ru

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье ставится цель дать данные о важности грамматики и методов, приемов обучения грамматическим правилам и конструкциям в общеобразовательной школе. В статье даны рекомендации по обучению грамматике с помощью кратких правил, а также приведены примеры.

Ключевые слова: грамматика, структура языка, преимущество, приемы, методы, подход, учителя, язык, дедуктивный метод, индуктивный метод, индуктивно-дедуктивный метод, случайный метод.

I. INTRODUCTION

Grammar is the first basis of every language structure. If there is a strong formation of grammar in any language, it is somehow easy to gain knowledge of that language. The more strong the grammatical structure is, the longer the language lives. It is obvious that every world language has a good grammatical basis and every aspect of the grammar of the world language is well learnt and studied worldwide. Which means, the power of a language is determined by its grammatical origin. Nowadays,

any language learner know that grammar is priority of language learning and without knowing grammar you are not able to speak, write and even listen. So from school times, teachers tend to teach everything related to a language from grammar.

As David Crystal, TES Teacher, said "Grammar is the structural foundation of our ability to express ourselves. The more we are aware of how it works, the more we can monitor the meaning and effectiveness of the way we and others use language. It can help foster precision, detect ambiguity, and exploit the richness of expression available in English".

One of the most sensible answers to the question of why grammar matters appears in a position statement on the teaching of grammar in schools. The report that was published by the National Council of Teachers of English (NCTE) is here:

"Grammar is important because it is the language that makes it possible for us to talk about language. Grammar names the types of words and word groups that make up sentences not only in English but in any language. As human beings, we can put sentences together even as children — we can all do grammar. But to be able to talk about how sentences are built, about the types of words and word groups that make up sentences—that is knowing about grammar. And knowing about grammar offers a window into the human mind and into our amazingly complex mental capacity. People associate grammar with errors and correctness. But knowing about grammar also helps us understand what makes sentences and paragraphs clear and interesting and precise. Grammar can be part of literature discussions when we and our students closely read the sentences in poetry and stories. And knowing about grammar means finding out that all languages and all dialects follow grammatical patterns"[1].

II. LITERARY REVIEW

Moreover, there are a lot of additional perspectives on grammar: "We study grammar because a knowledge of sentence structure is an aid in the interpretation of literature; because continual dealing with sentences influences the student to form better sentences in his own composition; and because grammar is the best subject in our course of study for the development of reasoning power"[2].

There are always advised and advanced methods of teaching any languages. While teaching a language, knowing grammar well is required from any teachers, so let's have a glance at several recommended methods to teach grammar in secondary schools.

There are few methods of teaching of grammar:

1. Deductive Method
2. Inductive Method
3. Inductive- Deductive Method
4. Incidental Method

1. Deductive Method:

- This method is also called the traditional method.

• In this method, grammar is an independent subject and taught with the help of a grammatical book. During this method a teacher uses a grammar text book, tells his students rules or definitions and then explains those with the help of examples then he gives exercise and asks his pupils to apply the rules. Students or pupils are supposed to memories the definition of noun. This method is not very effective as it is against the principles of teaching and students think that it is boring.

A. Advantages of Deductive Method

1. It is based on the theory “From generalization to example”.
2. This method helps students to compare the ideas in grammar of mother tongue and second or first language.
3. The learner can try the grammatical questions very easily.
4. Learner can respond effectively and can explain rules, structures, etc.

B. Disadvantage of Deductive Method

1. This method makes learner learning about language and cannot enhance communicative ability among learners.
2. The learners may be inactive during classroom teaching.
3. This method is not pupil -centered but teacher centered.
4. There is hardly use of audio visual aids in the classroom.

2. Inductive Method:

• Inductive method is also popular as informal method. In this method the teacher first presents or takes the example from the students then talks about theory of concept. This method implies teaching of grammar not by rules but by usage and practice. Through continuous practice of using words while speaking, reading and writing, grammar teachers can teach to students. By this method, practical uses of grammatical rules are elicited. But sometimes this method may become time consuming and lose the attention of the students.

A. Advantage of Inductive Method

1. Inductive method is based on the theory “From example to generalization”. And it is very helpful in classroom teaching.
2. This method helps students to understand the difference between particular notion in grammar.
3. This method is pupil-centered.
4. The learners learn the particular grammar point through use. First they have to deduce the meaning and later they generalize the form or structure.

B. Disadvantage of Inductive Method

1. This method is not useful in over crowded classes like can be found in many areas of the countries.
2. The institute must be ready to focus the language aspect, not the mark criteria. In this method the teacher has to use modern method of teaching language. Only an innovative teacher can use this method.

3. Inductive-Deductive Method:

• Through this method student they formulate rules with the help of examples. Some steps of this method are as follows. Students are given some examples of similar type.

- Students try to find out similarities by analyzing or observing these examples.
- Students are asked to draw some conclusions.
- Then the teacher will give the rules and give new examples and ask her pupils to verify the rules.

This method of teaching grammar proves very successful and advantageous as it becomes practical, real and scientific. It follows all the maxims of teaching and pupils are not forced to cram the rules. This method also stimulates the power of thinking and reasoning. Some shortcomings of this method are that it can be applied only to young learners. Moreover, this method is not complete in itself because sometimes students are unable to correlate examples with the topic.

4. Incidental Method:

This method is known and considered as correlation or reference method of teaching. This method helps to connect grammar with other related logical structures. Students have a knowledge of grammatical rules. Some disadvantages of this method are that it interferes with normal teaching.

III. METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Importance of grammar in development of communication skill:

- Grammar helps to learn correct pronunciation.
- With good grammar spoken or written words gain their meaning and value.
- Knowledge of grammar improves skill of expression.
- Grammar is also helpful in increasing accuracy. Grammar frames the mind to habits of order and clearness and also to logic and rhetoric. So, grammar rules can help learners develop a habit of thinking logically and clearly.
- Grammar also helps in acquiring fluency in a particular language. The person will also learn how to organize and express the ideas in his mind without difficulty.

Importance of grammar in development of writing skill:

- The learner learns to write with correct punctuation and correct language and spellings.
- With the knowledge of grammar, parts of speech etc. the child develops an effective writing style.
- Expression of feelings, emotions, frustrations in an impressive manner is possible only by knowledge of grammatical rules, syntax, vocabulary etc [3].

As teaching grammar needs a lot of efforts and responsibilities, there are some wise *techniques* to teach grammar at schools effectively.

IV. RESULTS

1. Direct Explaining (Explicit Approach).

You can explain a grammar rule directly using the students' mother tongue. This has the advantage of allowing students to contrast an item of grammar in English with

an item of grammar in the students' own language. For example, the two languages might use past tenses in different ways. On the other hand, some teachers believe that it's more effective to present and explain the grammar directly by using English at all times. Certainly, in classes where the students already have learnt some English, it's usually possible to build on what they already know to introduce a new grammar point.

2. *Discovering the Grammar (Implicit Approach).*

Often, it's helpful to have students discover the grammar rather than telling them what it is. Do this by choosing a text which contains lots of examples of the target grammar. For example, if the text includes regular verbs in the past simple form (e.g. lived, travelled, moved, etc), ask the students to underline all the verbs in the text. Then ask them to say what they notice about the verbs – which will be that they all end in -ed.

3. *Using Pictures or Drawings (Illustrating Grammar Points).*

A quick sketch on the board can illustrate a grammar point very quickly. For example, a picture of a person dreaming of a future ambition can be used to introduce "be going to" to talk about future intentions.

4. *Drawing Timelines (Teaching Tenses).*

Timelines are useful for teaching grammar structures that refer to aspects of time. Timelines are a simple and visual way to clarify the actions and events described in a sentence. They are often used by teachers for presenting the meaning of verb tenses in English. The basic form of a timeline shows a horizontal line with a point in the middle indicating NOW or the moment of speaking. Before that point is the past and after it is the future. Some teachers also write the words PAST and FUTURE along the line. You can indicate single actions with an X and periods of time with an arrow. Continuous actions are often indicated with a wavy line.

5. *Asking Concept Questions (Checking Understanding).*

Write a sentence on the board containing the grammar structure. For example, this sentence uses the past simple: He left university in 2008. Next, ask the students concept questions which check their understanding of when the action happened. So, the teacher/student conversation would sound like this:

T: Is he at university now?

SS: No.

T: Was the action in the past?

SS: Yes.

6. *Using Tables (Showing the Form).*

Tables are very useful for showing the form of the grammar on the board. For example, these tables show the affirmative and negative forms of a verb in the present simple tense. You can refer to the different features of the tense when introducing it, and the students can copy the table for future reference.

I/You/We/They live in Switzerland.

He/She/It lives in Switzerland.

I/You/We/They don't live in Switzerland.

He/She/It doesn't live in Switzerland.

7. *Using Objects (Presenting the Meaning).*

Sometimes using objects can work as quickly as anything to present the meaning. For example, if you want to present the comparative form (... is bigger than ...), the simplest way is to find two objects and contrast them. Alternatively, ask two students to stand up and compare their height to produce a sentence like: Hany is taller than Tom. Write the sentence on the board and underline the comparative form so the students notice the construction. Similarly, if you teach prepositions (in, on, next to, etc), using a selection of objects in different positions from each other is a very effective starting point.

8. *Contrasting Structures (Showing the Difference in Meaning).*

With higher-level grammar, it's useful to ask students to contrast two grammar structures which are similar in certain ways, but which have an important difference in meaning. For example, these two sentences contrast two different meanings of the present perfect tense.

He has been to Mexico.

He has gone to Mexico.

9. *Choosing the Correct Sentence (Correcting Common Grammatical Mistakes).*

This is similar to the previous technique because you give students two sentences, but one sentence has a mistake related to grammar. You write them on the board and get students to say which they think has the mistake and why [4]. For example:

I've been here since eight years.

I've been here for eight years.

V. CONCLUSION

As it is obvious from information given above, grammar is an intergral part of a language, and it is totally impossible to learn a language without gaining grammatical understanding. Nowadays, easy methods of teaching grammar are being launched, many advanced applications are invented to make grammar easy, overall, interactive, intensive lesson plans are being created by linguists to do a great favor for those who teach about languages.

REFERENCE:

1. <https://www.thoughtco.com/why-does-grammar-matter>
2. William Frank. – *The Teaching of English Grammar*. Houghton, 1905.
3. <https://www.adda247.com/teaching-jobs-exam/methods-of-teaching-english-grammar/>
4. <http://elttguide.com>